

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B163
Date: 26 Jan 2006
Take Off 07:57:11
Landing: 12:28:20
Flight Time 4h31m09

Campaign: DABEX
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Niamey local

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Aircraft Scientist	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	CCN / CVI / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	SWS / SHIMS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	AMS	Gerard Capes	University of Manchester
12	Wet Neph	Martin Glew	Met Office
13	VACC / PAN / tubes / bags	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
14			
15			
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20			

Flight Track:

B163 Track 26-JAN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B163

Date: 26 Jan 2006

Project: DABEX

Location: Over land area between Niamey, Banizoumbou and Djougou

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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073234		INU	0.77 kft	316	to nav
073359		GPS	0.77 kft	316	13' 28.65N 2' 10.53E
073543		CGPS	0.77 kft	316	Logging
075711		T/O	0.74 kft	087	Niamey
080316	081043	Profile 1	5.0 - 0.80 kft	276	missed approach to 50
080601		P1 interrupt	2.4 kft	358	
080819		P1 restart	2.4 kft	086	
080853		video	2.0 kft	086	#1 dfc #2 ffc
081043	083457	Profile 2	0.80 - 15.5 kft	087	50' fl160
081256		P2 interrupt	2.0 kft	083	2000'
081449		P2 restart	2.1 kft	301	
081922		P2 interrupt	6.0 kft	268	fl060
082133		P2 restart	6.0 kft	084	
082620		P2 interrupt	10.0 kft	086	fl100
082928		P2 restarted	10.0 kft	260	
083530		!	15.5 kft	265	manoeuvre
083801	084156	Profile 3	15.5 - 11.5 kft	070	
084214	084925	Run 1	11.5 kft	073	
085418	090702	Run 1.2	11.5 kft	238	
085458		heimann	11.5 kft	248	cal 11
091148	092519	Run 2	7.0 kft	076	
092848	094317	Run 3	4.1 - 4.0 kft	255	
093926		video	4.0 kft	250	#3 dfc #4 ffc
094838	100305	Run 4	2.0 kft	077	2000' qnh 1013
100621	102151	Run 5	3.0 kft	239	3000' qnh 1013
101641		heimann	3.0 kft	250	cal 14
102425	103751	Profile 4	1.3 - 15.0 kft	087	
103751	104522	Profile 5	13.1 - 10.5 kft	071	
104020		P5 interrupt	13.0 kft	071	
104227		restart P5	13.0 kft	275	
104522	105704	Run 6	10.5 kft	257	
104715		heimann	10.5 kft	256	cal 13
105704	110219	Profile 6	10.5 - 7.5 kft	255	
105840		P6 interrupt	9.0 kft	255	
110042		P6 restart	9.0 kft	079	fl 90 maneuvering
110219	111732	Run 7	7.5 kft	067	
111451		video	7.5 kft	069	#5 dfc #6 ffc
111904	112022	Profile 7	7.5 - 6.5 kft	261	
112023	113313	Run 8	6.5 kft	250	
112123		heimann	6.5 kft	253	cal 14
113313	114405	Profile 8	6.5 - 15.0 kft	251	
113801		P8 Interrupt	11.0 kft	251	
114004		P8 restart	11.0 kft	072	fl110
114405	115846	Profile 9	15.0 - 1.2 kft	066	
115846	121529	Run 9	1.2 - 1.4 kft	063	
115912		R9 interrupt	1.3 kft	096	
120024		R9 restart	1.3 kft	252	500' agl
120104		heimann	1.3 kft	253	cal 14
122820		Land	0.79 kft	086	
123700		INU	0.80 kft	316	13' 28.53N 2' 10.30E
123743		GPS	0.80 kft	316	13' 28.65 2' 10.53E

B163 Track 26-JAN-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DABEX: north-south sampling biomass burning plumes

Flight No: B163

Date: 26 January 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling at various altitudes of mineral dust and biomass burning aerosol around and to the south of Niamey.

Location:

Over land area between Niamey (13.54°N, 2.66°E), Banizoumbou (13.522°N, 2.629°E) and Djougou to the south (9° 45'36''N, 1°35'56''E).

Raster point #137 (13°38'N, 2°45'E)

Raster point #142 (13°23'N, 1°55'E)

Weather:

High loadings of mineral dust and biomass burning aerosols. Cloudless skies preferred. Terra overpass at 10:30, Aqua at 13:30, and Envisat at 10:26.

Special requirements:

Missed approach (50ft) over Niamey airfield and low-level (500ft) flying over land. Local racetrack sampling landing.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Niamey.
2. Ascend to 5000ft and carry out a missed approach descent to 50ft over Niamey airfield [15mins, T=15mins].
3. Broken profile ascent (turns at 2000ft, FL060, FL100) from 50ft to FL150 (or above the aerosol layer), at a rate of 1000ft/min [25mins, T=40mins].
4. Profile descent at 1000ft/min to FL100 to arrive at raster point #142 [5mins, T=45mins]
5. A series of four SLRs between raster point #137 and raster point #142 at heights to be decided by the aircraft scientist (e.g. FL100, FL80, FL60, and 500ft) [60mins, T=105mins].
6. Set of four orbits at 600ft (bank angle 60°) over Banizoumbou AERONET site [10mins, T=115mins].
7. A series of SLRs at three different altitudes (e.g. FL50, FL75, FL100) towards Djougou [45mins, T=160mins]
8. Set of four orbits at 600ft (bank angle 60°) over Djougou AERONET site [10mins, T=170mins].
9. Set of SLRs of 10minute duration at three different altitudes over Djougou (suggest FL50, FL75, FL100) [50mins, T=220mins].
10. A 'soft ride' terrain following low-level run at 500ft from Djougou towards Niamey [50mins, T=270mins].
11. Land at Niamey.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B163

Date: 26th January 2006

Sortie Objectives: DABEX flight #8. To investigate the in-situ properties and radiative properties of mineral dust and biomass burning aerosols together with the ULA aircraft.

Operating area: Mainly in the local area between raster point #137, and #142.

Raster point #137 (13°38'N, 2°45'E)

Raster point #142 (13°23'N, 1°55'E)

Weather: Cirrus cloud and medium level cloud to the south of the region meant that the proposed sortie to Cotonou could not be performed. A reduced sortie in conjunction with the ULA aircraft was successfully flown.

Flight Patterns: The ULA took off some 30 minutes prior to the take off of the Bae146. Subsequent to take-off, a missed profile descent and ascent (wheels and flaps down) was performed over Niamey airport to FL155. The profile was broken several times to keep the aircraft focussed on the vertical profile close to the airport. A reasonable amount of dust was present at lower levels with a nephelometer green scattering of $\sim 250 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ up to FL50, which suggests an aerosol optical depth for dust of around 0.3. The biomass burning contribution to the scattering was very much less than on previous occasions. The complicated layered structure of biomass burning aerosol had small peaks at FL70, FL80, and FL115 (nephelometer reaching 80, 80, and $100 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$). The main BB peak appeared to be between FL80 and FL150. CO and ozone profiles showed the usual correlation in the biomass burning layers, and the O3 showed the usual anticorrelation with the dust. SLRs were then performed at a series of different levels. Cirrus remained present throughout the flight, so SWS was used pointing downwards to get the spectral variability in the surface reflectance. Levels flown:

R1: FL115: Upper biomass layer

R2: FL70: Lower biomass layer

R3: 4000ft: Dust layer

R4: 2000ft: Dust layer

An email was received from Joss suggesting that the proposed relocation to Djougou was not a good option given that the cloud there was very extensive. Therefore the decision was made to continue working with the ULA, and the following SLRs were performed:

R5: 3000ft: Dust layer

Profile to FL150

R6: FL105: Upper biomass layer

R7: FL075: Lower biomass layer

R8: Lower biomass layer

Profile descent to low level

R9: 500ft 'soft ride': Lower dust layer

Summary: Excellent in terms of in-situ sampling. Radiation measurements will probably not be useful (except for the downward pointing SWS instrument). The data will be most useful in comparing against the ULA and the AMF and Banizoumbou lidar data.

Problems:

Wet nephelometer failed for the first part (dry neph worked well).

SWS and SHIMS – much better, but still not completely 4 out of 4 modules all of the time.

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.163**.....

Date ..26th Jan...2006.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Some Ci around. Thin & dissipating
					ULA T/O 45 minutes prior.
					ULA has downward lidar.
					7:50Z ULA reports FL150.
					220° 01 kt. V. little wind.
~ 07:58Z					T/O Niamey.
					A little low level haze, close to surface,
					stretching to ~ 5000ft
08:03:16	P1	FL50 ↓		13.4 ^N , 2.0E	Profile descent.
	Int P1	2300ft			Interrupt to go dirty (flaps & wheels)
	Restart P1	2300 ↓			
08:10:43	End P1 St P2	50ft ↑		13.4, 2.1	Profile will be broken at
08:12:56	Int P2	2000ft			2000ft, 6000ft, FL100, to FL150
08:14:49	Rest P2	2000ft ↑			Swap SHIMS → SWS, too much
					Ci to LHS, and overhead.
08:19:22	Int P2	6000ft			Dust from surface to
					5000ft.
					CO & O ₂ both increasing
					above 5000ft.
08:21:33	Rest P2	6000ft			Weak BB layers at
					FL70, FL80.
08:26:20	Int P2	10000ft			
08:29:28	Res P2	FL100 ↑			Lots of Ci about ~ 1/8
	End P2	FL155			
08:38:01	St P3	FL155 ↓			

FL105

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...163**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	FP3 St R1	FL115			Middle of BB layer (upper).
08:49:25	End R1	FL115			Neph green ~ $80 \mu m^{-1}$
08:54:18	St R12	FL115			
					Will do FL115 Sweep SWS to FL70 nadir viewing.
					4500ft
					MPA (soft ride).
09:07:02	End R12	FL115			Reposition & lose altitude in turn.
09:11:48	St R2	FL70			Middle of lower BB layer.
					Neph green ~ $80 \mu m^{-1}$
					Plenty of Ci around.
					SWS nadir viewing
09:25:19	End R3	FL70			Manoeuvre for FL40.
09:28:48	St R3	4000ft			In the dust layer at this altitude. Green scat ~ $270 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$
09:43:17	End R3	4000ft ↓			Reposition for low level run.
09:48:38	St R4	2000ft			Lowest constant pressure level.
					1013mb QNH. ~ 1200ft AGL.
					In thick dust Green scat ~ $320 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....163.....

Date26 Jan 2006.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	R4 cont				Dusty, still Ci around In situ sampling only.
10:03:05	End R4	2000ft		13.6, 2.7	Climb to 3000ft on reciprocal.
10:06:21	St R5	3000ft			3000ft is in the dust layer still. ULA operating over the airfield, so we'll displace slightly to the south.
10:21:21	End R5				
10:24:25	St P4	500ft		13.3, 1.8	Some light turbulence.
10:42:51	End P4 St P5	FL50			Above aerosol layers at FL150
10:40:20	Int P5	FL130			New levels:-
10:42:27	Rest P5				
10:45:02	End P5 St R6	FL105			
10:57:04	End R6 St P6	FL105			Profile down to FL75 (broken).
10:58:40	Int P6	FL90			Interrupt & turn
11:00:42	Rest P6	FL90			
11:02:19	End P6 St R7	FL75			Still lots of Ci around. Some evidence of waves in the neph scat - gravity waves? Also some turbulence felt (v. light). Concentrations of aerosol climbing along run from 50 → 80 × 10 ⁻⁶ μm ⁻³ .

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B163

Date: 26/01/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:03:16	160	0.12	Off	90	1											Start Profile 1 from FL050	
08:04:07	240	0.14	Off	80	1											FL040	
08:05:17	250	0.15	Off	80	1											FL030	
08:08:43	195	0.15	Off	80	10											FL020	
08:10:46	1600	0.09	0	70	10											End of Profile 1 @ 50	
08:12:54	210	0.16	0	80	10											FL020	
08:16:14	165	0.15	1	70	1											FL030	
08:17:20	190	0.14	2	70	1											FL040	
08:18:30	350	0.10	2	10	1											FL050	
08:19:21	360	0.10	2	10												FL060	
08:22:57	380	0.11	3	10												FL070	
08:24:04	400	0.11	3	10												FL080	
08:25:13	300	0.11	Off	5												FL090	
08:26:21	390	0.11	Off	5												FL100	
08:30:34	500	0.11	Off	10												FL110	
08:31:34	370	0.11	Off	5												FL120	
08:32:33	250	0.11	Off	5												FL130	
08:33:30	240	0.11	Off	5												FL140	
08:34:54	140	0.11	Off	2												End of Profile 2 @ FL155	
08:38:01	135	0.11	Off	2												Start Profile 3 from FL155	
08:39:34	330	0.12	3	2												FL140	
08:40:36	280	0.11		2												FL130	
08:41:54	590	0.12		5												End of Profile 3 @ FL115	
08:42:14																Start Run 1.1 @ FL115	
08:43:00	500	0.12		5													
08:45:00	510	0.12		10													
08:47:00	510	0.12		10													
08:49:00	525	0.12		10													
08:49:26																End of Run 1.1	
08:54:19																Start Run 1.2 @ FL115	
08:55:00	475	0.12		10													
08:57:00	490	0.12		10													
08:59:00	475	0.12		10	Fail											Restart SID2 as B163A	
09:01:00	420	0.12		10	Noise												
09:03:00	490	0.12		10	Noise												
09:05:00	500	0.12		10	Noise												
09:07:00																End of Run 1.2	
09:11:48																Start Run 2 @ FL070	
09:12:00	520	0.11		10	Noise												
09:14:00	560	0.11		10	Noise												
09:16:00	540	0.11		10	Noise												
09:18:00	530	0.11		10	Noise												
09:20:00	560	0.11		10	Noise												
09:22:00	600	0.11		10	Noise												
09:24:00	590	0.11		10	Noise												
09:25:19																End of Run 2	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B163

Date: 26/01/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:28:47																Start Run 3 @ 4000'	
09:29:00	210	0.14	Off	90	1												
09:31:00	240	0.14	Off	80	Noise												
09:33:00	200	0.14	Off	80	Noise												
09:35:00	240	0.14	Off	80	Noise												
09:37:00	210	0.14	Off	90	Noise												
09:39:00	240	0.14	Off	90	Noise												
09:41:00	235	0.14	Off	90	Noise												
09:43:17																End of Run 3	
09:48:39																Start Run 4 @ 2000'	
09:49:00	200	0.16	Off	100	1												
09:51:00	220	0.15	Off	100													
09:53:00	210	0.16	Off	100	1												
09:55:00	240	0.15	Off	100													
09:57:00	230	0.15	Off	100	1												
09:59:00	240	0.14	Off	100	1												
10:01:00	225	0.14	Off	100	1												
10:03:05																End of Run 4	
10:06:22																Start Run 5 @ 3000'	
10:07:00	220	0.14	Off	90													
10:09:00	210	0.14	Off	90													
10:11:00	235	0.15	Off	90													
10:13:00	250	0.14	Off	100	10												
10:15:00	260	0.14	Off	100													
10:17:00	260	0.14	Off	100	10												
10:19:00	240	0.14	Off	100	1												
10:21:52																End of Run 5	
10:24:24	1060	0.10	Off	100	Noise											Start Profile 4 from 500' agl	
10:25:14	195	0.15	Off	100	Noise											FL020	
10:26:24	210	0.14	Off	100	10											FL030	
10:27:13	160	0.14	Off	70	5											FL040	
10:28:04	360	0.10	Off	5	1											FL050	
10:29:02	435	0.10	Off	5	1											FL060	
10:29:51	480	0.11	Off	5	1											FL070	
10:30:51	325	0.11	Off	5	1											FL080	
10:31:55	380	0.11	Off	5	1											FL090	
10:32:51	485	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL100	
10:33:52	325	0.11	Off	5	Noise											FL110	
10:35:00	300	0.11	Off	5	Noise											FL120	
10:36:01	280	0.11	Off	5												FL130	
10:37:00	260	0.11	Off	5												FL140	
10:37:47	210	0.11	Off	5												End of Profile 4 & Start Profile 5 from FL150	
10:39:06	280	0.11	Off	5												FL140	
10:40:11	270	0.11	4	5												FL130	
10:43:33	360	0.12		5												FL120	
10:45:21																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 6 @ FL105	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B163

Date: 26/01/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:46:00	440	0.12	4	10	Noise												
10:48:00	500	0.12		10	Noise												
10:50:00	490	0.12		10	Noise												
10:52:00	510	0.12		10	1												
10:54:00	460	0.12		10	Noise												
10:56:00	400	0.11		10	10												
10:57:06																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 6 from FL105	
10:58:38	365	0.11		10	Noise											FL090	
11:01:43	405	0.11		10	Noise											FL080	
11:02:20																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 7 @ FL075	
11:03:00	425	0.11		10	Noise												
11:05:00	410	0.11	5	10	10												
11:07:00	480	0.11		10	10												
11:09:00	510	0.10		10	10												
11:11:00	560	0.10		20	Noise												
11:13:00	560	0.10		10													
11:17:19																End of Run 7	
11:19:03																Start Profile 7 from FL075	
11:20:23																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 8 @ FL065	
11:21:00	465	0.10	Off	10													
11:23:00	490	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:25:00	450	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:27:00	410	0.10	Off	10													
11:29:00	420	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:31:00	410	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
11:33:13	400	0.10	Off	10												End of Run 8 & Start Profile 8 from FL065	
11:34:48	345	0.11	Off	10												FL080	
11:35:54	330	0.11	Off	10												FL090	
11:37:01	300	0.11	Off	10												FL100	
11:37:59	300	0.11	Off	10												FL110	
11:41:19	240	0.11	Off	5												FL120	
11:42:14	240	0.11	Off	5												FL130	
11:43:10	220	0.11	Off	5												FL140	
11:44:06	180	0.11	Off	5	Noise											End of Profile 8 & Start Profile 9 @ FL150	
11:45:10	230	0.11	Off	5												FL140	
11:46:20	370	0.11	Off	5												FL130	
11:47:29	350	0.11	Off	5												FL120	
11:48:39	520	0.12	Off	5												FL110	
11:49:38	590	0.11	Off	5												FL100	
11:50:43	370	0.11	Off	5												FL090	
11:51:49	490	0.11	Off	5	Noise											FL080	
11:52:52	495	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL070	
11:53:58	450	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL060	
11:54:46	150	0.13	Off	60												FL050	
11:55:48	260	0.15	Off	100	1											FL040	
11:56:50	410	0.13	Off	100	1											FL030	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B163

Date: 26/01/2006
Operator: MAP
DRS Time: +0
DAU1 Time: +0
DAU2 Time: +0
DAU3 Time: +0
Aux1 Time: +0
Aux2 Time: +0
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:58:45	375	0.12	Off	100	Noise											End of Profile @ 500' AGL	
12:00:23																Start Run 10 @ 500' AGL	
12:01:00	375	0.12	Off	100	Noise												
12:03:00	400	0.12	Off	100	Noise												
12:05:00	400	0.12	Off	100	Noise												
12:07:00	390	0.12	Off	100	10												
12:09:00	800	0.14	Off	100	5												
12:11:00	500	0.12	Off	100	Noise												
12:13:00	420	0.11	Off	100	10												
12:15:00	310	0.13	Off	100	10												
12:15:33																End of Run 10	
	PCASP Flowrate = 1.8CC/Sec FFSSP switched off on occasions due to overheating SID 2 failed and needed to be restarted, noisy on occasions																

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B163

Date: 26/1/2006

Reprocessed by S Osborne 13/3/06

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	✓	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	✓	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	✓	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	✓	Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	✓	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 20s
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	✓	JT 11/02/06.
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		no nevz signal.
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B163

Date: 26/1/2006

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	✓	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	✓	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	✓	
4) Log on to FLOODS	✓	
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	✓	
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat iii) exit	✓	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	✓?	No AUX file produced (0 blocks)
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

<p>Preparation of imagery for Core data product</p> <p>iii) WAVE> auto_image</p> <p>a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:</p> <p>b) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD</p> <p>d) Enter start time 0 if unknown</p> <p>e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown</p> <p>f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">10</p> <p>iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files</p>	<p>PMSDATA:</p>	<p>FAAM, YYYYMMDD, R0, Bnnn, 2Dx-IMAGES.PS</p>
<p>ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC</p>		
<p>Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter</p>		
<p>Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files</p>		
<p>9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>b) Directory: PMSDATA:</p> <p>c) File generation: Hit enter</p> <p>d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data</p>		
<p>e) TAS: Y</p> <p>f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX</p> <p>g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">0 unless either probe known to be faulty</p> <p>h) Start time: 0 if unknown</p> <p>i) End time: 240000 if unknown</p> <p>j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5</p> <p>k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">11 if known to be in water cloud</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">8 if known to be in mixed-phase</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">8 if unknown</p> <p>l) Coefficient choice: 2</p> <p>m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>Note the particle type</p>
<p>10) In PVWAVE</p> <p>i) enter:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">!PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!</p> <p>ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'</p> <p>iii) exit</p>		
<p>11) MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D</p> <p>b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX</p> <p>c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name</p> <p>d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		
<p>12) CHECKS:</p>		
<p>i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?</p>		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B163

Date: 26/1/2006

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	✓	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ???? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: 0 if unknown h) End time: 240000 if unknown	✓	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate 1.6 cc/sec
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' iii) exit	✓	
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	✓	appears to be in mfd - though not logged @ time JT.

FLIGHT NUMBER: B163	DATE:	OPERATOR: PapJ	Page 1 of 2
PROJECT:			

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
0845					0.34	0.54	0.72	1.16	S
					836	1727	1968	3669	D
		16.36			107	104	104	233	B
		15.61			2321	2330	2343	2363	R
		14.5			967	967.9	967.8	967.9	P
		18.25		0.18	0.34	0.49	0.79	1.20	S
085418		17.38		240	702	997	1699	2626	D
		16.64		93	105	107	134	191	B
		15.9		2392	2400	2394	2396	2392	R
		14.88		967.8	967.8	967.6	967.8	967.7	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		18.78		0.18	0.34	0.54	0.78	1.18	S
91148		18.1		387	635	868	1123	1574	D
				113	112	112	127	127	B
		16.56		2361	2326	2322	2322	2322	R
		15.71		986.0	986	986	986	986	P
		19.42		0.18	0.33	0.54	0.75	1.16	S
		18.71		150	510	451	808	946	D
		17.97		77	178	82	88	88	B
092848		17.27		2393	2405	2414	2410	2407	R
		16.3		986	986	986	986	986	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		20.23		0.18	0.32	0.52	0.76	1.12	S
94832		19.55		157	318	489	646	705	D
		18.9		107	102	100	94	94	B
		18.06		2390	2300	2312	2324	2340	R
		17.04		985.8	985.9	985.8	985.8	986	P
		21.07		0.18	0.32	0.50	0.68	1.05	S
100621		20.45		92	283	288	597	538	D
		19.85		110	104	104	100	114	B
		19.11		2411	2372	2348	2317	2319	R
		18.13		985.5	985.5	985.5	985.5	985.5	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		23.04		0.17	0.31	0.51	0.69	1.09	S
104522		22.04		293	381	636	700	952	D
		21.62		128	128	126	122	123	B
		20.80		2349	2331	2330	2330	2330	R
		19.96		974	974	974	974	974	P
		23.47		0.17	0.32	0.48	0.71	1.10	S
		22.67		185	395	399	766	1213	D
110219		22.10		119	123	122	133		B
		21.22		2379	2384	2400	2400	2400	R
				986	986	986	986	986	P

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B163**.....

 Date **26/01/2006**

 Operator's name **M. GLEN**.....

 Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
Pre-flight	Zeroed	both Neph	Uninstalled + Reinstalled USB drivers.					
Reduced	Com 5 + Com 6 (USB 3+4)							to Com 2 and Com 2. Could ping Com 1, 2 and 4 with the nephelometer software. Disabled/Enabled 3, could ping that too.
Labview talking to	Dry	Wet	+ chiller	on Com 1, 2 and 3 (labview set default).				W/D ratios pre-flight. Red 0.92, green 0.9, Blue 0.9. Dry neph humidity 24%, Wet 66%
0818	P2	FL080	10.0	19%	66%	chiller off		1 finger in trap! where is it coming from.
0827	P2	FL100	10.2	27%	70%	chiller off		
0835	P2	FL155	10.1	12.5%	66%	chiller off		
0840	Labview	crash						coincident with opening chiller.
0936	P3	FL041	10.4	14%	44%	↑	+13°C	Chiller to +30°C. Still 1 finger in trap.
Dry is	on AS217	INST2						Net on AS218. INST2, USB 1+2.
0944			60.4	14%	64%	↑		Chiller to +40°C
0950	R4	2000'	10.5	11%	77%	↑		Chiller to +45°C
0958	R4	2000'	10.3	13%	85%	↓		Chiller to +30°C. 85% most RH I could get.
1000	R4	2000'	10.4	12%	69%	↓		RH decreasing fast!
1001	R4	2000'	10.4	13%	64%	↑		Chiller to +35°C
100305	Read	2000'	10.3	13%	65%			RH steady, Chiller at +35°C
100621	R5	3000'	10.5	13%	63%	↑		Chiller to +40°C
1010	R5	3000'	10.5	13%	70%	↑		Chiller to +42.5°C. RH steady at 70% at +40°C. ↑ +30°C
1013	R5	3000'	10.5	12%	75%	↑		Chiller to +44°C - RH steady at 75% at +42.5°C

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.163**.....

 Date **26/01/2006**

 Operator's name: **M. GLEW**.....

 Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1016	R5	3000'	10.5	11%	79%	↑		Chiller to +45°C. RH steady at +78% at T _{water} 44°C
102157	R5	3000'	10.5	12%	81%		+45°C	Altmaxes at 81%, T _{water} +45°C
1022	Chiller off for probe.							
104527	R6	FL105	10.2	14%	53%		+32°C	Chiller to +32°C
1047	R6	FL105	10.3	15%	53%	↑		Chiller to +40°C. (in) = 29°C
1050	R6	FL105	10.2	15%	67%	↑		Chiller to +42°C
1052	R6	FL105	10.3	15%	78%	↑		Chiller to +45°C
1055	R6	FL105	10.2	14%	80%	↓		Chiller to +40°C
1100	R6	FL090	10.1	15%	70%	↓		Chiller to +38°C
1102					68%	↓		Chiller to +36.5°C
110219	R7	FL075	10.4	16%	64%	↓		Chiller at +36.5°C
1103	R7	FL075	10.3	16%	65%	↑		Chiller to +39°C
1104	R7	FL075	10.4	17%	67%	↑		Chiller to +41.5°C
1106	R7	FL075	10.3	17%	72%	↑		Chiller to +43.5°C
1108	R7	FL075	10.3	17%	77%	↑		Chiller to +45°C
1111	R7	FL075	10.2	17%	82%	↓		Chiller to +42°C
1113	R7	FL075	10.3	17%	78%	↓		Chiller to +40°C
1114	R7	FL075	10.3	18%	74%	↓		Chiller to +37°C
111732	R7	FL075	10.3	18%	67%	↓		Chiller at +37°C
112023	R8	FL065	10.1	19%	64%		+36.2	

SWS

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 63	Date	26 JAN	Operator(s)	S. R. C. 2574	log page	1	of	2
Time	Run Id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

SHIMS

07 50 02	Taxing	—	DARK	150	500				
07 50 2		—	Scene	150	500				
07 57 08	TAKE OFF								
08 00 25			DARK	150	500				
08 00 39			Scene	150	500				T=18
08 03 16	P1 ↓	FL050							
08 10 43	P2 ↑	50'							T=19
08 15 57			DARK	150	500				
		SWS							Too much cir for SHIMS.
08 18 14			DARK	150	1000				
08 18		6 FSCENE		150	1000				T=20
08 32									Video recording on - see start of tape for image of PC clock
08 35		FLP55	DARK	150	1000				
08 35			6F	150	1000				NIR shutter failure? No - zero data to FL115
08 38 01	P3 ↓	FL115							Restarting to try to regain NIR.
08 41 15			DARK	150	1000				
08 41 35			6F	150	1000				
08 42 14	R1.1	FL115							
08 51 33			DARK	150	1000				
08 51 43			6F	150	1000				Thick Ci above T=20
08 53									→ Internal reflections in telescope (during heat) - can see back side of window mount
08 54 18	R1.2	FL115							
08 59 28			DARK						
09 00 27			DARK	150	500				
09 00 44			174A	150	500				← straight down (terrain) T=19.
09 11 48	R2	FL070							
09 24									Loss of NIR
09 25 36			DARK	150	500				(no NIR)
09 28 48	R3	FL040							
09 29			DARK	150	50				
09 29 25			174A	150	350				NIR is back
09 30 45			174A	150	350				
09 43 34			DARK	150	350				
09 44 39			174A	150	350				
09 48 38	R4	2000'							
10 03 18			DARK	150	350				
10 03 40			174A	150	350				T=18
10 06 21	R5	3000'							
10 22 18			DARK	150	350				

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B163

Date:

26 JAN 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 μm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1_a	B163Q1	----	----	Top	08:42:40	09:07:02	R1.1/R1.2	2220	FL115, very old biomass
Filters run1_a	B163N1	----	----	Bottom	08:42:40	09:07:02	R1.1/R1.2	1543	FL115, very old biomass
Filters run1_b	B163Q1	----	----	Top	09:11:48	09:25:19	R2	1527	FL070, continuing previous run in very old biomass
Filters run1_b	B163N1	----	----	Bottom	09:11:48	09:25:19	R2	1080	FL070, continuing previous run in very old biomass
Filters run 2_a	B163Q2	----	----	Top	09:28:48	09:43:17	R3	1729	FL040, dust layer, at the end of exposure I found out that the holder was not very well latched, so it might be contaminated
Filters run 2_a	B163N2	----	----	Bottom	09:28:48	09:43:17	R3	1188	FL040, dust layer
Filters run 2_b	B163Q3	----	----	Top	09:48:38	10:03:05	R4	1789	2000 feet, dust layer; changed as B163Q2 could be contaminated
Filters run 2_b	B163N2	----	----	Bottom	09:48:38	10:03:05	R4	1258	FL040, dust layer, continuing previous exposure
Filters run 2_c	B163Q3	----	----	Top	10:06:21	10:21:51	R5	1841	3000 feet, dust layer; continuing previous exposure
Filters run 2_c	B163N2	----	----	Bottom	10:06:21	10:21:51	R5	1313	3000 feet, dust layer; continuing previous exposure
Filters run 4_a	B163Q4	----	----	Top	10:45:22	10:57:04	R6	1058	FL115, very old biomass
Filters run 4_a	B163N4	----	----	Bottom	10:45:22	10:57:04	R6	649	FL115, very old biomass

Filter Sampling Log**Flight No:****B163****Date:****26 JAN 2006****Operator:****PFO**

Filters run 4_b	B163Q4	----	----	Top	11:02:19	11:17:32	R7	1524	FL075, very old biomass
Filters run 4_b	B163N4	----	----	Bottom	11:02:19	11:17:32	R7	1013	FL075, very old biomass
Filters run 4_c	B163Q4	----	----	Top	11:20:23	11:33:13	R8	1440	FL065, very old biomass
Filters run 4_c	B163N4	----	----	Bottom	11:20:23	11:33:13	R8	949	FL065, very old biomass
Filters run 5	B163Q5	----	----	Top	12:00:24	12:15:29	R9	1848	500 feet agl before landing, passing over Banizoumbou station around 12h05
Filters run 5	B163N5	----	----	Bottom	12:00:24	12:15:29	R9	1397	500 feet agl before landing, passing over Banizoumbou station around 12h05

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 163**

Date: 26th January 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	y	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	Y
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	Y

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B163

Date: 26th January 2006

Instruments

SHIM not operated - cirrus / SWS – OK

Cloud Physics – PCASP ok

FFSSP- switched off at low level,

2DC – noisy towards end of flight,

SID 2 noisy on occasions, otherwise ok

Core Chemistry – Ok

CCN - ok

CVI, ok

AMS – ok

Wet Neph – Problems with comms . calcs between wet & dry Neph inconsistent

VACC – ok,

PAN ok

Bags & tubes ok

Not fitted: ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls - Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B163:

Log	Reason
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet
Sun Photometer	No log sheet for this ground-based instrument is available.

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647
Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk